

Abstracts of presentations at the 45th Congress of the Israeli Phytopathological Society, February 16, 2026. Cohen Auditorium, Agriculture Research Organization – the Volcani Center, Bet Dagan, Israel.

Lectures

Development of a Three-Dimensional Biomimetic Root System for Studying and Isolating Root Parameters Influencing Root-Knot Nematode Behavior – Toward a Green and Eco-Friendly Solution

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The development of a three-dimensional biomimetic root system offers an innovative approach for studying and isolating principal root parameters that influence the behavior of root-knot nematodes (RKNs; *Meloidogyne* spp.). These nematodes are among the most destructive soil-borne pathogens in global agriculture, causing major yield losses in diverse cropping systems, including fruit trees, vegetable crops, and other economically important plants. Understanding nematode–root interactions is essential for developing effective and sustainable management strategies. In a collaborative effort between three research groups, we are combining complementary expertise to develop a prototype of a physical trap for plant-parasitic nematodes as a tool to reduce seedling infection during planting.

To address this challenge, we designed a synthetic platform integrating several biomimetic approaches, including solvent-casting for film formation, three-dimensional printing, and capsule-based emulsion techniques. Using combinations of natural polysaccharides, we produced stable films that mimic the composition of the plant root cell wall. Root-knot nematodes successfully penetrated these biomimetic structures, demonstrating the biological relevance of the system and its suitability for studying the early stages of nematode–root interaction.

To investigate the mechanisms underlying nematode penetration, we used glucose as an inhibitor of cellulase activity. This treatment reduced nematode entry into the biomimetic system, highlighting the central role of cell wall–degrading enzymes (CWDEs) in penetration of the synthetic root-like matrix. These findings, together with the integration of attractant compounds, support the development of an eco-friendly nematode trap.

In conclusion, this biomimetic platform provides a novel tool for identifying root traits linked to resistance or susceptibility to nematode infection and represents a step toward an applied, environmentally friendly solution.

Identification and Characterization of a Novel Orthotospovirus in Israel Affecting Tomatoes and Ornamental Crops

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In February 2024, unusual disease symptoms were observed in greenhouse-grown tomatoes in the Hefer Valley region. The symptoms included leaf yellowing and curling, accompanied by necrotic spots or rings; in some instances, plant wilting occurred. Symptomatic-fruits showed distortion, scarring, and developmental delays. These symptoms resembled those caused by tomato spotted wilt virus (TSWV). However, diagnostic analyses using enzyme-linked-immunosorbent-assay (ELISA) and RT-PCR ruled out the presence of TSWV, as-well-as other common tomato infecting viruses including the potyvirus potato-virus-Y (PVY), the cucumovirus cucumber-mosaic-virus (CMV), the tobamovirus tomato-brown-rugose-fruit-virus (ToBRFV), and the potexvirus pepino-mosaic-virus (PepMV).

To identify disease cause, viral RNA extracted from symptomatic leaves was subjected to sequencing using Illumina HiSeq. Bioinformatics analysis revealed the presence of a new species of ortho-tospovirus, encompassing three genome segments. Virus distribution and host range were studied with ELISA and western-blot tests using specific antibodies raised against the viral-nucleocapsid, as-well-as molecular identification using RT-PCR with primers designed according to the sequence of the new ortho-tospovirus.

Preliminary results indicate a broad viral host range that includes ornamentals. Symptomatic plants showed leaf necrosis in *Lisianthus* plants; floral distortion, yellowing, and leaf mosaic in *Cyclamen* plants; and leaf distortion and mosaic symptoms in *Gazania* plants. Literature indicates that the western flower thrips (*Frankliniella occidentalis*) and onion thrips (*Thrips tabaci*) serve as vectors for this virus. Ongoing research focuses on further characterizing host range among ornamentals; additional vegetable crops; and wild vegetation to develop effective strategies for mitigating the viral disease.

QTL Mapping and Identification of Markers for Resistance against Cucurbit Downy Mildew in Two Wild Cucumber Accessions, PI-197088 and PI-330628

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Cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) is a globally important vegetable. Its domestication has led to the narrowing of its genetic variation and high proneness to disease. Downy mildew, incited by the oomycete *Pseudoperonospora cubensis*, causes severe losses. Here, we studied the genetics of downy mildew resistance in cucumber, using two wild resistant accessions PI 197088 and PI 330628. To identify the QTLs responsible for resistance, we produced two mapping populations by crossing with the susceptible cultivar 'SMR': PI-197088 X SMR F2 and PI-330628 X SMR F2. Each F2 plant was evaluated for its resistance in detached leaves in the lab and in adult plants in the field. Two major QTLs were found to be responsible for resistance, on chromosome 4 and chromosome 5. Both were strongly and significantly associated with resistance in both populations. The QTL on chromosome 5 was highly consistent, affecting resistance at all evaluation time points in adult plants. In the PI 330628 X SMR F2 population, additional resistance QTLs were found on chromosomes 1, 2, and 6, which were not detected in the PI 197088 X SMR F2 population. This indicates that some genes for downy mildew resistance differ in the two wild accessions. An additional QTL was identified on chromosome 3 in both populations. Analysis of the genetic markers that represent the major QTLs on chromosomes 4 and 5 confirmed their contribution to resistance. Plants that inherited the marker allele from the resistant parent were significantly more resistant than plants that inherited the allele from the susceptible parent. Plants inheriting the resistance alleles from both chromosome 4 and 5 possessed the highest level of resistance. Our genetic markers provide a valuable tool for breeders. They can be used in Marker-Assisted Selection (MAS) programs to enhance the breeding of new cucumber cultivars with high and durable resistance to the disease.

Discovery of New Sources of Resistance to Bacterial Canker in Tomato

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Bacterial canker, caused by *Clavibacter michiganensis* (Cm), is one of the most important diseases affecting tomato crops worldwide. In this study, a screen of *Solanum pimpinellifolium* and *Solanum lycopersicum* var. *cerasiforme* tomato lines was conducted to identify new genetic sources of resistance to the disease. Out of 120 lines tested, two lines (30 and 62) displayed high tolerance, and one line (27) showed strong resistance. Characterization of the bacterium's ability to grow locally and systemically revealed that in these three lines, there was a significant reduction in Cm population compared with the susceptible line Moneymaker (MM). This finding suggests that the reduced disease severity is likely due to restricted bacterial growth or movement in the resistant lines. Monitoring defense response activation in the resistant lines showed increased transcript levels of *PR1a* and *PR5* upon infection compared with MM, indicating enhanced activation of defense responses. However, an HR-type defense response was not observed in any of the lines. To investigate the inheritance pattern of resistance, crosses were made between the resistant lines and the susceptible lines MM or M82, and resistance segregation was examined in the progeny of these crosses and their selfed offspring. The results showed that resistance in line 27 follows a dominant inheritance pattern, with a segregation ratio close to 3:1, suggesting that it is likely controlled primarily by a single locus. In contrast, resistance in the other lines was weakened and did not display a clear segregation pattern. In this study, we identified tomato lines exhibiting resistance or tolerance to Cm. These may serve as valuable resources for future breeding efforts.

Functional Validation of Candidate ZYMV Resistance Genes in Melon

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Zucchini yellow mosaic virus (ZYMV) is a major viral pathogen causing severe yield losses in cucurbit crops worldwide. In melon (*Cucumis melo*), resistance to ZYMV is controlled by a single locus, *Zym*, on chromosome 2. In the resistant accession PI414723, this locus contains two closely related candidate genes encoding CNL proteins (Coiled-coil, Nucleotide-binding, Leucine-rich repeat), sharing 88% nucleotide sequence identity, as well as a NAC family transcription factor. PI414723 was crossed with cultivar *Charéntais* generating two isogenic lines: *Charéntais ZymR* (resistant) and *Charéntais ZymS* (susceptible). Four CRISPR/*cas9* knockout constructs were generated: two that targeted each CNL gene separately, one targeting both, and a fourth construct targeting the NAC gene. Transformation of ZYMV resistant *Charéntais ZymR* leaf explants with the dual-CNL (BOTH) construct, yielded three independent transgenic-mutant plants, designated *Δb4*, *Δb5*, and *Δb6*. These carried mutations at all four target sites, two in each CNL gene. So far, inoculation experiments were conducted on the *Δb5* line, together with susceptible and resistant control plants. During six weeks of screening, the mutant plants exhibited typical mosaic disease symptoms comparable to the susceptible controls, indicating gene loss-of-function. This proves that one of the CNL candidates, or both, are responsible for ZYMV resistance. Potential interactions between the two resistance proteins and ten ZYMV viral proteins were also examined using transient expression in *Nicotiana benthamiana* and yeast two-hybrid assays. No evidence for direct protein interactions was found, and additional research on the mode of recognition of ZYMV by the melon R gene is required.

Tomato Yellow Leaf Curl Virus effects on the Endoplasmic Reticulum stress responses in *Bemisia tabaci*

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Tomato yellow leaf curl virus (TYLCV), a *Begomovirus* transmitted by the whitefly *Bemisia tabaci*, is a major threat to tomato production worldwide. Although the processes underlying virus acquisition and transmission have been widely investigated, the cellular immune mechanisms activated within the insect vector during virus transmission are poorly studied. The Endoplasmic Reticulum (ER) is a major organelle in the cell and plays a central role in coordinating stress responses such as autophagy and apoptosis during pathogen infection, making ER-associated pathways an important focus for studying virus–vector interactions. This study examined ER-linked immune responses in *B. tabaci* during TYLCV acquisition. Expression levels of the unfolded protein response (UPR) sensor proteins IRE1a, PERK and ATF6 were quantified using qRT-PCR and protein localization was assessed using immunostaining in viruliferous and non-viruliferous whiteflies. Viruliferous insects displayed elevated expression and enhanced localization of these ER stress sensors, indicating activation of UPR pathways during the acquisition of the virus. IRE1a showed the strongest induction, suggesting a prominent role in the insect’s response to TYLCV. Ongoing inhibition assays are being used to assess how IRE1a-associated pathways may influence viral accumulation, transmission or contribute to downstream processes such as apoptosis or autophagy. Overall, the findings highlight a potential involvement of ER stress and UPR signaling in the immune response of *B. tabaci* to TYLCV. These insights advance the understanding of virus–vector interactions and may support future efforts to disrupt TYLCV and other vector-borne plant virus transmission in agricultural systems.

Automated Detection of Mango Inflorescence Malformation Using Remote Sensing and Deep Learning

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Mango inflorescence malformation, caused by *Fusarium mangiferae*, poses a major threat to mango production in Israel and globally due to significant yield losses and reduced economic viability. The fungus penetrates plant tissue via bud bracts, leading to malformed sterile inflorescences that fail to set fruit and may cause yield losses of up to 50%. Infected inflorescences also serve as sources of reinfection for subsequent seasons. Current control strategies rely on fungicides and manual sanitation, which are costly (~20,000 NIS/ha) and only partially effective. This study aims to develop an automated tool for detecting inflorescence malformation using remote sensing and deep learning, to improve the accuracy and timing of sanitation operations and enable future robotic solutions. RGB imagery was collected via: (i) UAV flights at peak flowering (2022), (ii) close-range ground photography of the ‘Keitt’ cultivar (2023), and (iii) ground photography of additional cultivars (‘Lilly’ and ‘Kent’) at varying phenological stages (2024–25). Deep learning models using UNET architectures were trained and evaluated for accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity. Results showed that UAV imagery with 1.1–1.3 mm/pixel resolution was insufficient, whereas ground imagery with 0.2–0.6 mm/pixel enabled accurate identification of malformed inflorescences, achieving up to 94% average precision and F1-scores of 0.89 (malformed) and 0.84 (healthy). Model performance was highest when training and testing were aligned in cultivar and phenological stage. Future research will focus on improving model generalization, enabling early detection prior to peak bloom, and adapting the approach to UAV-based and robotic disease management workflows.

Characterization of Postharvest Pathogens in Stored Carrots and the Development of Sustainable Control Strategies

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The fungicide Rovral (a.i.: Iprodione 50% v/v) was banned for use as a postharvest treatment of long-term cold-stored carrots (0–2°C for 6–10 months) in late 2020. As a replacement, Scholar (a.i.: fludioxonil 230 g/L) was registered for commercial use on January 2021. To prevent the potential development of resistance to fludioxonil, the goal of the present study was to elucidate the etiology of decay-causing pathogens of cold-stored carrots and develop integrated and sustainable decay management protocols. A total of 101 fungal isolates were recovered from infected carrots collected from commercial cold storage facilities across Israel. Koch's postulates were completed, and pathogenic isolates were evaluated for their aggressiveness to carrot at 5°C and 16°C. Ten *Botrytis cinerea* (gray mold) and eleven *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* (white mold) isolates were identified as the most aggressive to carrot. One and three *S. sclerotiorum* isolates were classified as resistant and tolerant to fludioxonil, respectively. The resistant isolate exhibited high sensitivity to osmotic stresses and did not accumulate intracellular glycerol in the presence of fludioxonil. In contrast, the sensitive and tolerant isolates highly accumulated intracellular glycerol and were significantly less sensitive to osmotic stress. Next, combinations of fludioxonil with inorganic GRAS salt compounds, (calcium chelate; CaDTPA, and ammonium bicarbonate), were evaluated for their efficacy as postharvest dipping treatments. Combining CaDTPA with half of the commercial concentration of fludioxonil inhibited growth of all isolates, including the resistant one, indicating a potential for the development of an improved postharvest treatment.

Bacteriophages as potential biological control agents against the plant-pathogenic bacterium *Paracidovorax citrulli*

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Paracidovorax citrulli is the causal agent of bacterial fruit blotch (BFB), a destructive disease of cucurbit crops worldwide, particularly melons and watermelons. Current BFB management relies mainly on copper-based bactericides, which pose environmental risks and promote the emergence of copper-resistant *P. citrulli* strains, highlighting the need for sustainable and environmentally friendly alternatives. Bacteriophages (phages) have recently emerged as promising biocontrol agents within integrated pest management frameworks. The aim of this study is to isolate *P. citrulli*-infecting phages and to characterize their potential as biological control agents. Six phages exhibiting lytic activity against *P. citrulli* strain M6 and additional *Paracidovorax* spp. were isolated. Phages were characterized based on propagation efficiency, host-range, and genomic analysis. Host-range assays revealed that the phages infect multiple *P. citrulli* strains, while some strains, including AAC00-1, were resistant to all tested isolates. Whole-genome sequencing of two phages showed 100% identity and coverage with prophages present in the genomes of several *P. citrulli* strains, including AAC00-1. Notably, filtered supernatants from AAC00-1 cultures induced plaque formation on M6, whereas M6 supernatants did not infect AAC00-1. Further analysis demonstrated that one phage isolate (P4) can integrate into the M6 chromosome, generating a lysogenic strain tolerant to phage infection, likely via superinfection exclusion. These results indicate that prophages harbored in resistant *P. citrulli* strains can be released and infect susceptible strains of the same species. Ongoing work focuses on additional phage isolation, host–phage interaction studies, and evaluation of selected phages in planta for their ability to reduce BFB severity.

Shape-Shifting Stones: Peptide-Infused Minerals for Next-Generation Antifungal Protection

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Postharvest fungal contamination leads to substantial crop losses and continued dependence on chemical fungicides. This study presents a biodegradable peptide delivery system using calcium carbonate (vaterite) microparticles to stabilize and release the antifungal peptide NCR13_PFV2 to inhibit *Alternaria alternata*. Vaterite particles were synthesized with or without polymer coatings of dextran sulfate sodium (DSS), polystyrene sulfonate (PSS), or β -cyclodextrin (β -CD). Morphological analysis by SEM confirmed the distinct surface structures and stability of each polymer-modified carrier. Peptide loading and release assays revealed that DSS and PSS exhibited the highest encapsulation efficiencies and sustained release profiles, with DSS maintaining peptide delivery for over a week. Fungal inhibition assays showed significant suppression of *A. alternata* growth by peptide-loaded DSS and PSS particles compared with controls, at both pH 5.5 and 7.0. Confocal microscopy and optical tweezers confirmed strong adhesion between polymer-modified vaterites and fungal hyphae, supporting a mechanism of localized sustained peptide delivery. Compared with free peptide, encapsulation provided enhanced stability and prolonged bioactivity. In a postharvest *in-vivo* assay using pepper fruits (*Capsicum annuum* cv. "Pepperito"), peptide-loaded DSS and PSS formulations reduced fungal disease development by 66.5% and 77%, respectively, compared with untreated controls. These results demonstrate that sulfonated vaterite composites are efficient, low-cost, and biodegradable carriers for antifungal peptides in postharvest protection. DSS offered the most sustained release, while PSS provided strong particle-fungus adhesion, suggesting complementary mechanisms that could be combined in future designs. This programmable vaterite-based platform advances sustainable alternatives to synthetic fungicides, aligning with environmentally-conscious agricultural practices and improved food security.

Bringing a Novel Pathogen Nucleic-Acid-Based Fungicide to Market: Development Journey and Key Learnings from Gilboa™

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Developing a new fungicide with a novel mode of action remains one of the most complex and resource-intensive processes in modern crop protection. ADAMA is advancing Gilboa™, a first-in-class Pathogen nucleic-acid-based molecule (Group 32 by the FRAC) designed to provide a new solution for managing a wide range of diseases, including Septoria in wheat

Developing Gilboa™ required establishing a robust technical synthesis pathway for the molecule, alongside identifying formulation concepts that protect the active ingredient and ensure reliable delivery into plant tissues, taking into consideration agriculture's diverse regulatory frameworks, and anticipating its role in resistance-management programs.

Across multiple trials, Gilboa™ consistently protected the leaf canopy, resulting in improved crop performance under diverse growing conditions. Additional studies evaluated its compatibility with integrated disease-management programs, its environmental behavior, and its potential to mitigate resistance pressure due to its distinct mechanism of action that supports reliable Septoria and other disease control and helps secure yield and farm profitability—key expectations from growers and advisers.

Overall, the journey of Gilboa™ demonstrates the multifaceted effort required to bring a new mode of action to the market and highlights the importance of cross-functional alignment, persistence and adaptability when pioneering innovative solutions for global agriculture.

New Azoxystrobin Clay Carrier to Eco-Friendly Control Corn Late Wilt Disease

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Corn late wilt disease (LWD), caused by *Magnaporthe oryzae*, poses a major threat to corn production in highly affected regions, with its global relevance intensifying under climate change. This study aims to broaden LWD management beyond resistant varieties, whose immunity may be compromised under high disease pressure. Here, we evaluated a novel approach utilizing clay-based carriers for the slow release of Azoxystrobin (Az). A growth-room experiment showed that during the disease's latent stage (40 days post-sowing), the sepiolite-Az formulation increased shoot biomass by 61%, although qPCR analysis indicated that infection levels remained high. A full-season potted trial revealed substantial benefits when sepiolite-AS and bentonite-AS were applied directly to the seedbed. At 42 days post-planting, these treatments markedly improved plant survival (191% and 64%, respectively) and enhanced phenological development (175% and 67%, respectively), accompanied by a nearly 95% reduction in root infection. By harvest (78 days), bentonite-AS was particularly effective, increasing shoot biomass by 128% and ear yield by 135%, while reducing shoot symptom severity by 42% and nearly eliminating detectable pathogen DNA. The combination of sepiolite-Az with *Trichoderma*-based seed coating nearly doubled shoot biomass relative to infected controls and suppressed pathogen root infection to near-zero levels ($p < 0.05$). These findings demonstrate that clay-based controlled-release fungicide formulations can effectively mitigate LWD impacts while reducing fungicide usage. Targeted spot application reduces the need for repeated treatments, providing a cost-effective and environmentally friendly strategy compatible with diverse agricultural systems and potentially extendable, through integration with biological agents, to other soil-borne pathogens.

Low-Tech - High Applicability: Translating research into plant protection solutions in orchards and vineyards

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Modern agriculture increasingly adopts high-tech solutions, yet many require long development and testing periods. We have focused on simple (low-tech) technologies that can be rapidly integrated into disease management, improving efficacy, reducing environmental impact, and lowering resistance risk. These approaches are inexpensive, easy to develop and test, and quickly implementable in orchards and vineyards. Three technologies were evaluated: ozonated water sprays, hot air applied with a heat blower, and fungicide applied via a permanent spraying system (PSS) with overhead sprinklers. Experiments were conducted during 2017 to 2025 in vineyards and mango and apple orchards against powdery mildew, apple scab, and fruit rot. Weekly or biweekly ozonated water sprays in vineyards reduced powdery mildew incidence and severity on grape clusters by 85–100%, similar to chemical fungicides. Ozonated water reduced apple powdery mildew incidence and severity by 50–78% and 60–85%, respectively. Hot air application at 180–230°C was safe to all three crops. Treatment at 180°C reduced apple powdery mildew incidence and severity by 50–70% and reduced mango powdery mildew severity by 90%. Combining hot air or ozonated water with fewer fungicide sprays reduced powdery mildew incidence by 60–90% and severity by 85–90%, comparable to or better than standard grower programs. Fungicide application via PSS (7–10 min every 7–14 days) effectively reduced powdery mildew and scab in apple orchards by 90–100% and fruit calyx rot by 70–80%, similar to or greater than air-blast spraying. Integrating these technologies can reduce chemical inputs, lower resistance risk, decrease costs, and maintain effective disease control. All three technologies evaluated are ready for commercial application, and some are already in use in orchards and vineyards.

Inhibition of white mold disease (*Athelia rolfsii*) in industrial tomatoes using black soldier fly secretions: from laboratory to field

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The soil-borne fungus *Athelia rolfsii* is a necrotrophic pathogen with a broad host range, causing collar and fruit rot in summer crops, including industrial tomatoes. Current disease management relies mainly on chemical fungicides, whose use is increasingly restricted, emphasizing the need for sustainable biological alternatives. Black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens*) larvae are used for agricultural waste degradation, generating frass that is rich in organic matter and microorganisms. This study evaluated the suppressive potential of different frass types against *A. rolfsii* and assessed the role of the frass microbiome in pathogen inhibition. Non-sterile frass extracts, primarily derived from larvae fed apple waste and bear industry residues, significantly inhibited *A. rolfsii* mycelial growth in vitro on PDA medium ($p < 0.05$), whereas sterile extracts showed no inhibitory effect. *Pseudomonas* sp. was identified as a key antagonistic bacterium, reducing mycelial expansion by approximately 50%. In pot experiments, frass application reduced disease progression in industrial tomatoes and increased plant biomass by 30–60% and canopy cover by ~40% in infected plants. Field trials with artificially inoculated seedlings demonstrated a strong positive correlation between frass concentration and plant height and node number ($R^2 \approx 0.98$), along with a significant reduction in plant mortality ($p < 0.01$). Overall, the results indicate that black soldier fly frass functions as a microbiome-driven, disease-suppressive amendment with strong potential for integration into sustainable and integrated crop management systems. Soil samples were collected for further analysis of frass-induced changes in the soil microbiome.

Exploring a green alga isolated from the Negev desert for sustainable biological control of soil-borne diseases

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ABSTRACT

The application of biological control agents (BCAs) offers a promising path toward reducing chemical pesticide use in sustainable agriculture. Nevertheless, the complex interactions between BCAs and their biotic and abiotic environments pose significant challenges to developing effective solutions. Utilizing a resilient BCA along with a better understanding of how environmental factors influence its antifungal activity may increase the chances of successful implementation of the BCA in the field. A green alga isolated from desert biological soil crusts shows a remarkable ability to withstand harsh environmental conditions. Preliminary findings indicated that this alga significantly inhibits the growth, viability, and melanin production of several pathogenic fungi. Among these, *Rhizoctonia solani* was selected as a model organism due to its susceptibility. Our results demonstrate that varying abiotic factors such as salinity, carbon, light and temperature levels impact the alga antifungal activity. Notably, supplementing the growth medium with 0.1M NaCl significantly enhances its antifungal effect, suppressing growth and melanin production. Building on these findings, this study aims to examine the ability of the green alga to inhibit the pathogenic activity of *Rhizoctonia solani* in plants and to elucidate the inhibition mechanism of the antifungal compounds. In parallel, we are trying to isolate and characterize the antifungal compound. This research seeks to advance our understanding of algae-fungi interactions in the soil, and the influence of environmental conditions on this interaction. Ultimately, this will allow the successful implementation of sustainable solutions for managing soil-borne pathogenic fungi.

Keywords: Biological control agents (BCAs), green algae, *Rhizoctonia solani* and antifungal activity

The Effect of Water and Temperature Stress on the Outbreak of Charcoal Rot (*Macrophomina Phaseolina*) in Sensitive Cotton Variety

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Abstract

Global cotton yield losses due to biotic constraints are estimated at almost 30%, and these impacts have intensified with climate change. A notable example is the increased incidence of charcoal rot caused by *Macrophomina phaseolina* (Tassi) Goid., particularly affecting the more sensitive Pima cultivars whose cultivation is expanding. The fungus can infect asymptotically, with disease expression largely dependent on environmental stressors such as temperature fluctuations and water availability. *M. phaseolina* tolerates broad temperature and rainfall ranges, with the minimum temperature of the coldest period contributing significantly to its predicted future spread. However, the reasons behind its present resurgence remain unclear. Earlier studies have shown that adequate irrigation reduces disease incidence, yet excessive watering promotes vegetative growth at the expense of reproductive development. Farmers often sow on moist soil to utilize stored rainwater, which often require earlier sowing at lower soil temperature and necessitates deeper seed placement. To assess how this early stress affects charcoal rot development, a three-year field experiment was conducted. The findings revealed that lower soil temperatures during early growth prolonged germination and increased plant susceptibility to *M. phaseolina*. Furthermore, early planting weakened the plants, enhancing vulnerability to infection and reducing yield. These results suggest that early sowing to allow wet-soil planting conditions is suboptimal, as it favors disease outbreak. Nevertheless, phenotypic data alone remain inconclusive. Consequently, a new research project has been initiated to elucidate the molecular interactions among the host, pathogen, and cold stress during the early developmental stages.

Premature Field Collapse in Spring Potatoes: Field Assessment and Fungicide Efficacy Screening in the Western Negev, Israel

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Abstract

In recent years, potato production in the Western Negev of Israel has been increasingly affected by premature field collapse during late growth stages in the spring season. The disorder begins with necrotic leaf spots resembling *Alternaria alternata* infection but is characterized by rapid collapse within 10–20 days after symptom onset and poor control by commonly used fungicides. As this phenomenon is newly emerging, comprehensive field assessment and fungicide screening are required to reduce its impact. This study aimed to determine the spatial and seasonal distribution of the collapse and identify effective fungicides for its management. Forty potato farms were monitored weekly during the 2024/25 growing seasons, including 19 winter and 21 spring fields. Disease distribution was assessed using ground surveys combined with real-time remote sensing data. Twelve fungicides were screened *in vitro* against *A. alternata* using the food poisoning method, and selected compounds were evaluated under field conditions using a randomized complete block design. Although initial symptoms were observed in both seasons, collapse occurred exclusively in spring-grown potatoes, affecting approximately 45% of farms and significantly reducing yield ($P = 0.007$). Varietal responses differed, with Celtiane being the most sensitive cultivar. NDVI showed a strong negative correlation with foliar infection level ($r = -0.639$, $p < 0.0001$), reflecting rapid canopy deterioration following disease escalation. Although *A. alternata* was the most frequently isolated pathogen, artificial inoculation failed to reproduce full plant collapse, and common fungicides showed low efficacy. These findings highlight the need to replace older compounds and further investigate the underlying causes of rapid field collapse.

MAP-1 Family Effectors MjMAP19 and MjMAP40 Drive Parasitism and Immune Suppression in *Meloidogyne javanica*

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Abstract

Root-knot nematodes (RKNs) are devastating plant parasites that deploy secreted effectors to manipulate host physiology and suppress immunity. The *Meloidogyne* avirulent protein-1 (MAP-1) family has been implicated in early host–parasite interactions, yet its functional roles remain poorly defined. Here, we characterize two MAP-1 family members from *Meloidogyne javanica*, MjMAP19 and MjMAP40, which were identified in oxylipin-induced pre-parasitic J2 (ppJ2) transcriptomes. Fluorescence *in situ* hybridization localized both transcripts to amphid neurons, supporting their roles in host perception and early signaling. Both genes were strongly induced in ppJ2s and sharply downregulated upon parasitism, with *MjMap40* displaying a markedly steeper transcriptional shift. *In planta* localization revealed targeting of both effectors to the endoplasmic reticulum and Golgi apparatus. Transient expression in *Nicotiana benthamiana* showed that MjMAP19 and MjMAP40 suppress Gpa2/RBP-1–mediated programmed cell death and reduce ion leakage, demonstrating their capacity to inhibit effector-triggered immunity. Overexpression in tomato hairy roots enhanced gall formation and nematode reproduction, confirming virulence functions. Conversely, *in vitro* RNA interference significantly impaired host recognition and root penetration, establishing their essential roles during early infection. Despite overlapping activities, the two effectors exhibit distinct regulatory features. MjMAP19 retains expression and activity at elevated temperature, whereas MjMAP40 shows loss of temperature responsiveness, sharper expression decline, and signatures of functional erosion, suggesting divergent evolutionary trajectories. Collectively, our findings identify MjMAP19 and MjMAP40 as amphid-secreted virulence effectors that suppress host immunity and promote feeding-site establishment, providing new mechanistic insight into MAP-1 family function, effector diversification, and temperature-dependent breakdown of host resistance.

Quantifying Latent Infection Dynamics of Postharvest Fungi Using Biosensor-Derived Disease Metrics and RT-LAMP

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Postharvest fungal pathogens are a major cause of decay in fresh produce, leading to substantial economic losses worldwide. A critical challenge in postharvest disease management is the ability of fungi to establish latent asymptomatic infections in fruit and vegetables, before progressing to visible decay. Early identification of these latent inoculations is therefore essential for informed decision-making to reduce postharvest loss. In this study, a biosensor-assisted framework was used to characterize disease progression and latent infection dynamics in fruits caused by *Alternaria alternata*, *Penicillium expansum*, and *Botrytis cinerea*. Disease development was monitored using severity index and incidence curves, enabling identification of latency termination and peak decay stages. The effects of fungal inoculum load on decay progression were quantified. Molecular validation of latent infections was performed using reverse transcription loop-mediated isothermal amplification (RT-LAMP) to detect fungal presence prior to visible symptoms. Strong linear relationships ($R^2 = 0.99, 0.928, \text{ and } 0.947$) were observed between inoculum concentrations of *A. alternata*, *P. expansum*, and *B. cinerea*, respectively, and their corresponding AUDPC values and RT-LAMP signals, demonstrating the biosensor's capacity to detect and semi-quantify latent fungal infections. This integrated epidemiological and molecular approach provides a robust tool for detection of the latent fungal infection long before postharvest decay occurs, supporting proactive management strategies to minimize losses and improve postharvest decision-making.

Enhancing Plant Resistance against *Botrytis cinerea*: Effects of *Rhodotorula toruloides* and Novel Graphene Oxide Elicitors

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Botrytis cinerea is a necrotrophic fungal pathogen causing substantial yield losses across many crops multiple plant developmental stages. Control still relies largely on chemical fungicides, whose repeated use raises environmental concerns and promotes the emergence of resistant pathogen populations. This study examines plant immunity-oriented approaches to suppress *B. cinerea*, focusing primarily on the oleaginous yeast *Rhodotorula toruloides*, alongside the evaluation of phytohormone-based graphene oxide (GO) novel elicitors.

In vitro assays demonstrated strong inhibition of *B. cinerea* following exposure to *R. toruloides* secretions, including complete suppression of pathogen growth at early incubation stages and sustained inhibition over time. These findings support antibiosis as a plausible mode of action against the pathogen. Further modes of action by which *R. toruloides* may act against *B. cinerea*, including resource competition and activation of plant defense responses, are also being investigated.

As an additional elicitation strategy, Auxin and kinetin-based formulations associated with GO were tested on greenhouse grown tomato. A seed-coating application protocol was calibrated, and identified concentration that do not compromise plant development. Treatment with Kinetin+GO induced a mild but consistent alteration in leaf phenotype, indicating a sustained physiological effect that is currently being assessed in long-term growth experiments. The impact of the different elicitor treatments on *B. cinerea* development on tomato plants was also evaluated.

These findings highlight the potential of biological tools as practical alternatives to conventional chemical disease control and support the development of microorganism-based approaches for reducing fungal diseases in plants.

Antifungal Potential of Grape Pomace Polyphenols in Postharvest Control of *Botrytis cinerea*.

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Postharvest losses account for more than 40% of global fruit and vegetable production, with fungal decay representing a major contributor. Currently, synthetic fungicides remain the most effective method of control; however, their widespread use poses risks to human health, beneficial microorganisms, food safety, and environmental sustainability, while also contributing to resistant fungal strains. Therefore, there is an urgent need for greener alternatives. Phenolic compounds are integral to plant defense and the precursor for the phenylpropanoid pathway. Exhibiting antioxidant, antimicrobial and antifungal properties. Grape pomace—the solid by-product of the wine industry—retains up to 70% of the phenolic content of grapes and represents millions of tons of waste annually worldwide. Valorizing this underutilized by-product could both mitigate waste and provide natural antifungal agents. Preliminary findings indicate that grape pomace phenols inhibit *Botrytis cinerea*, with concentration-dependent fungicidal (>0.6 mg/mL) and fungistatic (>0.2 mg/mL) effects, alongside fungal physiological changes. This research investigates three primary questions: (1) Can the phenylpropanoid pathway be induced in grape pomace to enhance phenolic production? (2) Does flavonoid hydrolysis increase antifungal activity? (3) Do certain pomace compounds inadvertently promote fungal growth? Using molecular, biochemical, and inoculation assays to evaluate gene expression, enzyme activity, flavonoid profiling, and extract efficacy in controlling fungal growth and fresh produce decay. The study highlights grape pomace's potential as a sustainable, bioactive alternative to synthetic fungicides.

Eco-Friendly Trichoderma Management of Fusarium Basal Rot in Onion

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Basal rot disease (FBR), caused by *Fusarium* species, poses a global threat to onion production, with damage occurring throughout the entire crop cycle. The present study evaluated Trichoderma-based protection against major Fusarium pathogens in Israel through a series of experiments, from in vitro antagonism and seed assays to a semi-field pot trial spanning a full growing season. In confrontation assays, 10 out of 15 *Trichoderma* strains exhibited strong inhibitory activity against the *Fusarium* complex associated with the disease. Among the most effective isolates, *T. asperellum* (P1), *T. longibrachiatum* (T7407), and *T. beinertii* (T14707) consistently demonstrated significant antagonism through both secreted metabolites and volatile compounds. Unlike other *Trichoderma* strains, these three caused moderate effects on seed germination and early growth. Seed assays further revealed cultivar-dependent sensitivity, with the Orlando yellow cv. more susceptible than the Maadim red cv., and *Neocosmospora falciformis* emerging as the most aggressive pathogen. Seed coatings with selected *Trichoderma* strains, tested under semi-field conditions, significantly promoted plant growth, with effects evident as early as mid-season. Shoot fresh biomass increased by 54–131% compared with untreated controls, accompanied by parallel improvements in other growth parameters. At the end of the season, *T. asperellum* treatments outperformed others, significantly enhancing shoot weight (28–119%) and bulb weight (15–157%) under pathogen stress. This growth promotion was accompanied by up to 36% reduction in shoot symptoms and 59% infection suppression (tracked by qPCR). Overall, the study demonstrates the promise of Trichoderma-based seed treatments as an effective, sustainable strategy for managing onion FBR.

Downy Mildew Resistant Beit Alpha Cucumbers

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Downy mildew, caused by the oomycete *Pseudoperonospora cubensis*, is the most destructive foliar disease of cucumbers. Slicer cultivars (with spined fruits) having partial resistance against downy mildew are commercially available on the market, but resistant cultivars of the Beit Alpha type (characterized by smooth, dark green fruit) have not yet been developed. Here, we report on the successful breeding of downy mildew-resistant Beit Alpha (BA) cucumber lines (1). Resistance was transferred from the wild Sikkim cucumber accessions PI 197088 and PI 330628 (characterized by round fruit, with heavily netted brown rind). The two PI lines were crossed together and the F1 was crossed with the BA type Dlila. The resistance and fruit phenotype of the F2 plants were restored through backcrosses to the elite BA commercial susceptible cultivars Rome, Nena, Katrina and Deloux, ending with the creation of four highly resistant BA lines. Due to the recessive nature of the resistance genes and their distribution across some chromosomes (see Hammer and Cohen in this meeting), the breeding program lasted more than ten years and required multiple backcrosses and stringent selections for both resistance and fruit type.

1. Hammer, R.S.; Ben Naim, Y.; Brand, A.; Cohen, Y. 2025. Transfer of Downy Mildew Resistance Genes from Wild Cucumbers to Beit Alpha Types. *J. Fungi* 2025, 11, 597. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof11080597>

Characterizing the Immune Response Induced in *Nicotiana* species by *Clavibacter* Serine Proteases

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Clavibacter is a genus of plant-pathogenic bacteria that causes significant damage to a wide range of agricultural crops. Solanaceous-associated *Clavibacter* species rely on the secretion of serine proteases from the Chp/Pat-1 family for virulence. In addition to their role in disease, several Chp/Pat-1 proteases trigger host-dependent hypersensitive responses (HR) in resistant solanaceous plants, indicating a dual function in virulence and immune recognition. To investigate this, we used an *Escherichia coli* delivery system to screen 20 Chp/Pat-1 homologs for HR induction across fifteen solanaceous species representing five genera. Only three proteases, ChpG and Pat-1 from *Clavibacter michiganensis* (Cm) and Chp-7 from *Clavibacter sepedonicus*, elicited HR, with recognition patterns varying among hosts. Eggplant was the only *Solanum* species to exhibit HR and responded exclusively to ChpG. In contrast, *Nicotiana* species showed pronounced, species-specific responses: ChpG induced HR in *N. sylvestris* and *N. glutinosa*, whereas Pat-1 and Chp7 induced HR in *N. sylvestris* and *N. tabacum*. No HR was observed in *N. benthamiana*, *N. glauca*, *N. rustica*, or *N. sanderae*. These species-selective patterns were confirmed using Cm mutants lacking *chpG* and *pat-1* complemented with individual proteases. Virulence assays further revealed that while some *Nicotiana* species, such as *N. tabacum* and *N. glauca*, were resistant to Cm regardless of Chp/Pat-1 composition, specific homologs exerted host-dependent positive or negative effects on virulence in *N. sylvestris*, *N. rustica* and *N. glutinosa*. Our data demonstrate that differential recognition and function of Chp/Pat-1 proteases in *Nicotiana* are key determinants of immune activation and host range in *Clavibacter*.

Transcriptomic and Functional Analyses Reveal JA-Dependent Immune Responses to the *Clavibacter* Effector ChpG in Eggplant

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Plant resistance to pathogens is facilitated through the recognition of secreted pathogen effectors, leading to rapid activation of immune responses. The secreted protease effector ChpG from the tomato pathogen *Clavibacter michiganensis* (Cm) serves as a host-specificity determinant that elicits a hypersensitive response (HR) and restricts bacterial colonization in the non-host eggplant. This study aims to characterize the molecular mechanisms underlying ChpG recognition in eggplant. RNA-seq analysis comparing eggplant leaves infiltrated with Cm wild-type or Cm $\Delta chpG$ mutant identified 5,144 ChpG-dependent differentially expressed genes (DEGs) at 12 hours post-inoculation, which were validated by RT-qPCR. KEGG enrichment revealed that ChpG strongly activates defense-associated pathways, including α -linolenic acid metabolism, while suppressing photosynthesis and other growth-related processes. Genes involved in the biosynthesis of key defense hormones—salicylic acid (SA), ethylene, and jasmonic acid (JA)—were significantly upregulated in response to ChpG, a pattern further confirmed by phytohormone quantification in Cm-infiltrated tissues. To functionally assess whether ChpG-induced genes and pathways contribute to its recognition, we used Virus-Induced Gene Silencing (VIGS). Silencing the JA receptor *SmCOII* or a strongly ChpG-induced LBD-regulated transcription factor, *SmLOB*, attenuated ChpG-mediated HR. Consistent with these results, treatment with the JA biosynthesis inhibitor DIECA reduced ChpG-triggered HR, confirming that ChpG recognition is JA-dependent. Furthermore, transient overexpression of *SmLOB* triggered cell death in *Nicotiana benthamiana*, suggesting that *SmLOB* functions as a positive regulator of HR. Together, these findings reveal that ChpG recognition relies on JA-dependent signaling and identifies *SmLOB* as a key component of the ChpG-induced HR pathway.

Contribution of Jasmonic Acid Signaling to ChpG-Induced Hypersensitive Response in Eggplant

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The Gram-positive plant pathogenic bacterium *Clavibacter michiganensis* (Cm) secretes multiple virulence factors, including the serine protease effector ChpG, which acts as an avirulence determinant in eggplant by inducing a strong hypersensitive response (HR) and conferring immunity against the pathogen. The downstream host signaling pathways contributing to ChpG-mediated HR are not fully resolved. This study investigated the contribution of jasmonic acid (JA) signaling to ChpG-mediated immunity in eggplant using Virus-Induced Gene Silencing (VIGS). Eggplant homologs of *AOC*, (JA biosynthesis), *COII* (JA perception), and *MYC2* (JA-responsive transcription) were transiently silenced using the TRV system. Silencing efficiency was confirmed by RT-qPCR, showing 50–80% transcript reduction, and by the characteristic photobleaching phenotype of *PDS*-silenced control plants. To assess immune responses, silenced plants were infiltrated with Cm, and HR was evaluated visually and by ion-leakage assays. While robust HR was observed in control plants, treated with TRV:*GFP*, *COII* silenced plants exhibited a clear reduction in HR intensity, whereas silencing of *AOC* or *MYC2* had no substantial effect on HR development. These results suggest that JA perception via *COII* contributes to ChpG-mediated HR. Together, these findings demonstrate that JA signaling, specifically through *COII*, modulates ChpG-triggered immunity in eggplant and establish a functional framework for dissecting immune signaling pathways involved in resistance to Gram-positive bacterial pathogens.

Environmental and molecular insights into *Pectobacterium brasiliense*, *dickeya solani*, and soft rot resistance in potato seed tubers

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Abstract

Soft rot and blackleg are destructive bacterial diseases that cause severe damage to the agricultural ecosystem, especially potato cultivation. These diseases are caused by two bacterial genera, *Pectobacterium* and *Dickeya*, belonging to the Soft Rot *Pectobacteriaceae* (SRP) family. The progression of the disease outbreak involves a sudden shift in the bacteria within the seed tubers, transitioning from a dormant state to an aggressive phase that causes severe damage to crops. This complicates early detection and hinders timely eradication efforts. Environmental conditions, particularly temperature, appear to be critical in triggering this transition. However, the exact conditions required for this shift have not yet been clearly defined. Due to the complexity, this study aims to understand the effect of temperature on bacteria and seed tubers separately before examining the effect of temperature on their interactions. Culturing the bacteria at various temperatures and measuring optical density at 600nm to generate growth curves provided insights into their behavior under different thermal conditions. The effect of preheating at 33°C was tested on potato tubers from four varieties (Tyson, Nyeta, VR808, Smith's Comet). Surprisingly, the rot intensity of the variety Smith's Comet shows improved resistance after preheat treatment. Therefore, the pre-heat treatment was conducted with Smith's Comet under different temperatures for different durations. Our findings suggest that both bacterial thermal response and heat response of the tubers affect disease development and might help design disease-controlling strategies; upcoming molecular studies on heat-treated tubers will further explore the underlying mechanisms.